

Popular Financial Report 2022

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Popular Financial Report

Public entities are increasingly turning to Popular Financial Reports (PFRs) as a tool to respond to the growing demand for accountability and transparency. "Popular Financial Reporting" describes a more comprehensive strategy for making financial and performance data more approachable and clear to the general public. PFRs are now required because of worries that traditional government financial reports, although precise and thorough, frequently fall short of giving the public a thorough grasp of how the government spends public money. Government actions may come under increasing public suspicion and mistrust as a result of this lack of transparency. PFRs have therefore been developed in response to these worries, with the goal of reestablishing trust in the way public funds are handled and spent (Yusuf et al., 2013).

Ucla

S T R U C T U R E

01.

Methodological note and
Dissemination plan

02.

UCLA overview

03.

Mission & Values

04.

Rankings

05.

UC Group Administration

06.

UCLA Administration

07.

Personell

08.

Financial Statements

09.

Education and Didactics

10.

Research

11.

Third Mission & Impact

12.

UCLA Environmental
Responsibility

13.

References

Methodological note

This section provides an overview of the research methodology and processes used to gather and analyse the data presented in the Popular Financial Report for the University of California, Los Angeles, for the year 2022.

In this report, we face various aspects of the institution, including administration, personnel, financial performance, education, research, environmental responsibility, and the economic impact on California.

Data Sources

We collected data from a variety of sources, including University Records and the Publicly Available.

- **University Records:** collected by UCLA's financial statements, academic records and institutional publications on UCLA website
- **Publicly Available Information:** such as rankings, U.S. News & Report data were used to supplement and verify the data gathered from UCLA

Data Compilation and Verification

Datas collected were carefully gathered, organised and verified to ensure accuracy and consistency. Subsequently, data was reviewed for completeness and consistencies.

Data Analysis

Datas are organised into distinct sections, dedicated to a specific aspect of UCLA.

Different analytical approaches have been used to analyse such datas, such as Trend Analysis and Comparative Analysis.

Citation and Attribution

Every data and information used in this report, was appropriately cited and attributed to their original sources.

Acknowledgement

We acknowledge that despite every effort to ensure accurate and reliable information, errors or omissions must be taken into account.

In summary, this methodological note provides essential insights and the rigorous and transparent approach employed in creating the Popular Financial Report for UCLA in 2022 for the comprehensive analysis of the university's data.

Dissemination Plan

The objective of UCLA's Popular Financial Report is to ensure its wide distribution and that it reaches stakeholders, including students, faculty, donors and the general public. In order to reach the public, we provide some dissemination channels such as

- social medias such as our LinkedIn profiles here below:

- the European journal of volunteering and community-based projects website [European journal of volunteering and community-based projects \(odvcasarcobaleno.it\)](http://odvcasarcobaleno.it)

UCLA overview

The university of California – Los Angeles, also known as **UCLA** is a well-known and esteemed public research institution in the United States that is situated in the Westwood neighborhood of Los Angeles, California. It was created in 1919 as a result of the State Normal School, a former university that had been formed in 1882 to train teachers. It is the second-oldest campus in the University of California system, behind Berkeley. It has:

 32,423 Undergraduate Students

 14,007 Graduate Students

 5,247 International Students

 7,941 Faculty Members

 106 Countries Represented by Students.

Mission & Values

As a public research institution, UCLA's main goal is to create, disseminate, preserve, and use knowledge for the benefit of society at large. UCLA is dedicated to academic freedom in its purest form in order to carry out its mission: "We value freedom from intolerance, free and lively debate conducted with mutual respect for individuals, and open access to information." It aims for diversity and excellence in everything it does because it knows that genuine quality comes from transparency and inclusivity. Its three institutional responsibilities—public service, research, and education—are based on these ideals.

Mission & Values

The land-grant missions of UCLA—public service, research, and education—are upheld. The goal of the university community is to promote critical inquiry, open discourse, inventiveness, and creative teamwork. This commitment fosters the personal and professional development of all staff, administrators, educators, and students in an inclusive setting. A warm and inclusive environment for all members of the campus community is largely facilitated by these Principles of Community.

EDI RELEVANCE

The Office of Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) at UCLA is a leading authority on initiatives related to improving diversity, inclusion, and equity; safeguarding civil rights; and maintaining dignity for all members of the community.

The EDI Network

A vast network of EDI-related student organizations and alumni networks, faculty/staff EDI leaders, and EDI-focused committees/councils is committed to the work of advancing equity, diversity, and inclusion for all Bruins.

Rankings

UCLA performs well in all of the national and international rankings of public and private universities, including the most widely known list published by U.S. News & World Report.

National Rankings:

#1 Public University

U.S. News & World Report, 2023

This year, UCLA joins UC Berkeley as the nation's No. 1 public university, ranking 20th among all national universities in the U.S. News & World Report Best Colleges rankings.

#7 Best Colleges for Veterans Among National Universities

U.S. News & World Report, 2023

Rankings

#9 World Reputation Ranking

Times Higher Education, 2020 UCLA ranked 9th out of 100 universities in the Times Higher Education World Reputation Rankings. These rankings are derived only from the opinions of senior, published academics from around the globe.

#13 Global Ranking

U.S. News & World Report, 2022

U.S. News introduced a new global ranking of universities in 2014. Differently from the publication's U.S. ranking system, it gives much more weight to academic research and reputation, as well as graduate and professional school quality.

#15 World University Rankings

Times Higher Education, 2021

UCLA was 15th overall among the top 1,102 universities in the world in the respected Times Higher Education World University Rankings. The rankings is based on performance measure such as the quality of teaching, research and the global blend of staff and students.

#9 World Reputation Rankings for Research

UC Group Administration

The University of California (UC) system, of which UCLA is a member, was established in 1868 when Governor Henry H. Haight signed the Organic Act, which established the state's first "complete university."

The governor of California appoints the **Board of Regents**, which is in charge of overseeing the UC system. The Regents select the University of California **President**, the 10 chancellors, and the directors and deans who oversee the operations of the various campuses and divisions of the university in addition to establishing overall policy and deciding on the UC system's budget. The **Academic Senate**, which sets academic policy for the University of California as a whole, is given jurisdiction in academic affairs by the Regents. The Senate, which is made up of academic staff members and a few administrative officials, sets requirements for enrollment and degree conferrals, approves and monitors courses and curriculum, and counsels UC administration on matters pertaining to faculty hiring and advancement.

Each campus academic policy is set by local sections of the Academic Senate, which is the university-wide body. Students are also involved in systemic and campus policymaking. (University of California System, 2023)

University of California (2023), University of California System

More can be found by click on this symbol

UCLA Administration

The roles:

The **Chancellor**, together with the **Executive Vice Chancellor and Provost**, oversees the almost 43,000 students, 4,300 faculty members, and 42,000 staff members of UCLA in addition to the \$7.5 billion budget. In addition, the chancellor has an important external role as a thought leader who collaborates with colleagues globally to address opportunities and issues facing UCLA and public higher education in general.

Vice-Chancellors hold key positions in the university's administration and academic departments. He or she is in charge of the University's Council, the Faculty General Board, and the University Finance Committee.

Vice Provosts oversee and carry out important faculty-wide academic projects. Additionally, they offer recommendations and strategic advice on academic issues that could have an impact on the university.

Deans of the College are academic leaders in charge of the academic, administrative, programmatic, and financial aspects of every school. In addition to awarding degrees and assessing instruction, deans are in charge of recruiting, admitting, and counseling students as they pursue their academic goals.

Personnel

The **UCLA Workforce Report** (below) presents the number (headcount) and FTE (full-time equivalent, including UCLA academic and administrative employees, such as staff and students).

The FTE is based on split appointments (partial FTE is credited to each organization/division and Workforce Category as appropriate)

Headcount: based on primary appointments, in order to not double count heads.

UCLA comprises thousands of professionals across various fields, they play very important roles in academic excellence, research, and student support. From accomplished faculty members to administrative staff and healthcare professionals at the renowned UCLA Medical Center, this talented workforce fosters innovation and inclusivity, and drives the institution's mission to educate, inspire, and positively impact society.

Gender Distribution

UC Academic Workforce Diversity

Race / Ethnicity

Age group

UC Non-Academic Workforce Diversity

Gender

Race / Ethnicity

Age group

Balance Sheet

Assets, Deferred Outflows & Inflows, Liabilities, Net Position

(in millions of dollars)	2022	2021	2020
ASSETS			
Investments	\$8,182	\$8,779	\$6,441
Accounts receivable, net	1,266	1,144	977
Capital assets, net	7,816	7,934	7,602
Other assets	370	389	365
Total assets	17,634	18,246	15,385
DEFERRED OUTFLOWS OF RESOURCES			
	2,533	2,274	3,227
LIABILITIES			
Debt, including			
commercial paper	6,412	5,989	4,866
Net pension liability, including pension			
payable to UCOP	5,923	2,670	5,765
Net retiree health			
benefits liability	4,412	5,491	5,188
Other liabilities	2,036	1,999	1,868
Total liabilities	18,783	16,149	17,687
DEFERRED INFLOWS OF RESOURCES			
	2,792	4,035	2,056
NET POSITION			
Net investment in			
capital assets	1,967	2,574	2,979
Restricted:			
Nonexpendable	347	345	333
Expendable	2,154	2,294	1,689
Unrestricted	(5,876)	(4,877)	(6,132)
Total net position	\$(1,408)	\$336	\$(1,131)

UCLA's financial situation at the conclusion of each year is shown in the Statement of Net Position.

Investments

There are 4 different pools of investments managed by the University. STIP (Short Term) used to manage the normal running operational needs, with a positive return of 2.1 percent in 2022. TRIP (Total Return) for long term investments in large pools. BGP (Blue Gold Pool) are investments done in equity and fixed income markets while still keeping liquidity (negative return (15.2) percent in 2022). GEP (General Endowment) are investments in balanced portfolio more heavily weighted towards equities (e.g. return (7.6) percent in 2022).

Annual Financial Report 2022

We will focus on the financial statements for the fiscal year 2021/2022, which ended on 30th June 2022 (academic year)

Balance Sheet

Assets

Assets are resources with an economic value, owned or controlled by the company and are useful to it to generate revenue.

UCLA's assets and deferred outflows of resources totaled \$20.2 billion in 2022. Net capital assets have decreased due to depreciation and disposals in excess of continued investments in facilities. Investments decreased in 2022 due to negative financial market returns.

Capital investments are primarily driven by UCLA's growing enrolment and ongoing needs for renewal and modernization of existing facilities. The rapid rate of capital spending persisted in order to provide the facilities required to support UCLA's research and teaching. In capital spending are included buildings for academic use, research laboratories, libraries, student services, parking structures, and infrastructure projects.

The University records alterations in the fair values of interest rate swaps that are designated as hedging derivatives, losses resulting from debt refundings, asset retirement obligations and specific shifts in the net pension and net retiree health benefits liabilities as deferred outflows of resources.

Balance Sheet

Debt & Other liabilities

Liabilities are obligations for the company which, due to events happened in the past, involve money owed by the company to its creditors.

UCLA's liabilities and deferred inflows of resources increased to \$21.6 billion in 2022. Liabilities increased in 2022 due to the increase in the liability for pension benefits. A range of funding sources, such as stock contributions, government funding, gifts, revenue bonds, bank loans, and leases, are used to finance capital assets. Bank loans and commercial paper offer interim financing for capital assets during the construction period. UCLA's debt, which is used to primarily finance capital assets, includes \$37 millions of commercial paper outstanding at the end of 2022. Total debt outstanding was \$6.4 billion at the end of 2022. Commercial paper is primarily used as financing for short-term financing for other needs. Other liabilities consist of accounts payable, accrued salaries, other employee benefits, unearned revenue, and federal refundable loans. Deferred inflows of resources regard gains on debt, refunding and changes in the net pension and net retiree health benefits liabilities.

Income Statement

(In millions of dollars)	2022		
	Operating	Non-operating	Total
REVENUES			
Student tuition and fees, net	\$975		\$975
State educational appropriations		\$696	696
Direct government grants		136	136
Federal Pell Grants		51	51
Grants and contracts, net	1,306		1,306
Medical center, net	3,321		3,321
Educational activities, net	2,790		2,790
Auxiliary enterprises, net	439		439
Private gifts, net		404	404
Investment income, net		137	137
Other revenues	217	80	297
Revenues supporting primary activities	9,048	1,504	10,552
EXPENSES			
Salaries and wages	4,482		4,482
Pension benefits	942		942
Retiree health benefits	256		256
Other employee benefits	1,092		1,092
Scholarships and fellowships	205		205
Utilities	85		85
Supplies and materials	1,420		1,420
Depreciation and amortization	494		494
Interest expense		204	204
Other expenses	1,622	94	1,716
Expenses associated with primary activities	10,598	298	10,896
Income (loss) from primary activities	(1,550)	1,206	(344)
OTHER NONOPERATING ACTIVITIES			
Net appreciation (depreciation)			
In fair value of investments			(982)
Income (loss) before other changes in net position			(1,326)
OTHER CHANGES IN NET POSITION			
State capital appropriations			1
Capital gifts and grants, net			22
Additions to permanent endowments			4
Transfers			(445)
Increase (decrease) in net position			(1,744)
NET POSITION			
Beginning of year, as previously reported			336
Cumulative effect of accounting change			
Beginning of year, as restated			336
End of year			\$(1,408)

Revenue is the total income generated by a business through its primary activities.

Revenues to support UCLA's primary activities, including those classified as nonoperating revenues, were \$10.6 billion in 2022.

The diversity of funding sources has significantly grown during the last few years.

Expense is the cost incurred by the company in the process of conducting its regular business operations.

Expenses associated with UCLA's primary activities, including those classified as nonoperating expenses, were \$10.9 billion in 2022.

Net position is the difference between assets, liabilities, deferred outflows, and deferred inflows. UCLA's net position was \$(1,408) million in 2022.

2022 Revenues (in millions of dollars)

Annual Financial Report 2022

Net student tuition and fees were \$975 million in 2022. The difference between the amount that the student and third parties pay on their behalf, and the declared price for tuition and fees, is known as scholarship allowances or financial aid and in 2022, netted against student tuition and fees, were \$232 million. In 2022, UCLA received fundings in order to lessen the effects of decreased revenue and higher expenses associated with COVID-19 under certain provisions of the Coronavirus Aid, Relief, and Economic Security (CARES), Coronavirus Response & Relief Supplemental Appropriations (CRRSA), and American Rescue Plan (ARP) Acts. **UCLA received \$103 millions to provide emergency financial aid to students.** Revenue from federal, state, private and local government grants and contracts was \$1,306 million in 2022

2022 Expenses (in millions of dollars)

Annual Financial Report 2022

Approximately two-thirds of UCLA's expenses are related to salaries and benefits. There were 38,440 full-time equivalent (FTE) employees in 2022. Total salaries and benefits increased by 12.1% in 2022, primarily driven by the increase in pension expense of \$570 million and salaries and wages of \$288 million. Salaries increased by 6.9%, comprised of an increase in the number of full-time equivalents and an increase in the average salary per full-time equivalent. As part of its commitment to affordability, UCLA gives financial aid for students: it was given \$489 millions in all financial aid's forms. Scholarships and fellowships expense, representing payments of financial aid made directly to students and reported as an operating expense, were \$205 million. In 2022, increases in housing costs, tuition, fees, and enrollment are all in line with increases in financial aid, scholarships, and fellowships.

Cash Flows

The Campus' Cash Flows	
Cash flows (in millions of dollars)	2022
Cash received from operations	\$8,802
Cash payments for operations	(9,202)
Net cash used by operating activities	(400)
Net cash provided by noncapital financing activities	1,264
Net cash provided by operating and noncapital financing activities	864
Net cash provided (used) by capital and related financing activities	(671)
Net cash provided (used) by investing activities	(271)
Net increase in cash and cash equivalent	(78)
Cash and cash equivalent, beginning of year	1,558
Cash and cash equivalent, end of year	\$1,480

Annual Financial Report 2022

The cash flow statement provide information about the cash inflows and outflows.

The cash received from operations sums up to \$8,802 and cash paid for operations sums up to \$(9,202). The (0,4) \$ millions of higher cash-out vs cash-received is basically due to operational tasks.

State educational appropriations, as well as private donations and grants, are among the revenue flows that the campus depends on for basic operational support of its core instruction function. In 2022, net cash of \$671 million was utilized for capital and related financing activities, mostly for principle and interest payments as well as purchases of capital assets. The proceeds from debt issuance and commercial paper financing helped to offset some of this amount. Net cash of \$271 million was used in 2022 for investing activities

Education and Didactics

Wide range of undergraduate, graduate and professional degree programs across various sectors (*letters, sciences, arts and architecture, education and information, law, management, theatre and television, nursing, dentistry, medicine...*). Nonetheless, it's a very restrictive university, in 2022 just **9% of the applicants were admitted**.

Applied	Admitted	Enrolled	Admit Rate	Yield
149,815	12,844	6,462	9%	50%

Despite this very strict admission rate, the number of students attending the various faculties is quite high and representative of the importance of the university in the Californian scenario.

Education and Didactics

Number of students enrolled in 2022: 46,430

In the two graphs are represented the distribution of scholars among the different faculties of the university both for undergraduate students (for a total of **14007**) and for graduate students (for a total of **32,423**). In 2022, the total number of enrolled students (both undergraduate and graduate students) was indeed **46430**.

Education and Didactics

Aim of the didactics: promote collaboration among students and prestigious ex-students (very successful and often leaders in the respective fields) to produce valuable researches.

The university does indeed contribute in a significant way, financially supporting researchers.

Furthermore, the campus is constantly growing and enhancing tools (as the presence of an actual hospital inside the campus), in order to create a scholarly community and creative space for students.

The objective is to grow successful individuals with a unique set of skills.

Following, data collected by UCLA's research on average earnings two years after graduation by UC bachelors major.

Education and Didactics

Education: At first, students receive a very broad education before specialising in a discipline. Generally speaking, the education is both theoretical and practical (when allowed), and strongly supports the creation of debate in class. The community works together to advance knowledge, and learning extends beyond the classroom and external communities.

Students' life on campus: very stimulant, offers a wide range of organisations, clubs and extracurriculars activities. The university in fact, values the importance of the school sports team: *the UCLA Bruins*.

Bruins participate to the NCAA division I-A as part of the Pacific -12 Conference. Some of the athletes that started their career at UCLA got the chance to gain some serious accomplishments. As instance, UCLA obtained several Olympic medals in different disciplines.

Research

With more than **\$1 billion** in annual external research funds, UCLA is one of the best research universities in the world. Numerous state and commercial organizations, as well as federal institutions including the National Institutes of Health, the National Science Foundation, NASA, the National Endowment for the Humanities, and DARPA, fund UCLA researchers. UCLA offers world-class research and scholarship in a wide range of fields, including the humanities, arts, medicine, and engineering.

	NEW RESEARCH FUNDING	RESEARCH EXPENDITURES	REQUESTED NEW RESEARCH FUNDING	NEW INVENTIONS DISCLOSED
FY 21 STATS	\$1.6B	\$1.2B	\$5.1B	423
FY 22 STATS	\$1.7B	\$1.35B	\$4.7B	327

Being one of the best research universities in the world, UCLA possesses the vast research resources and intellectual capital needed to take on the most difficult problems facing society. Furthermore, we take seriously our responsibility as a public research university to provide solutions that raise standards of living locally, nationally, and globally. The faculty, graduates, and researchers include **three Pulitzer Prize winners, two Turing Award winners, a Fields Medalist, fourteen Nobel Prize winners, and thirteen faculty MacArthur Fellows.**

6,000 active research projects on campus

\$1 billion in research funding received by UCLA each year

40% of undergraduate students work on faculty research

#9 World Reputation Rankings for Research
Times Higher Education (2019)

The **UCLA Technology Development Group** is the entry point for innovation, research, and entrepreneurship on campus. Its goal is to:

- Encourage UCLA's entrepreneurship, innovation, research, and teaching for the good of society.
- Provide economic benefit to the State of California and UCLA's academic and instructional goals.
- Organize the research community at UCLA to commercialize innovations.

There are currently over **1,000 active U.S. patents** in UCLA's portfolio, and this figure is continually rising.

Innovation have been led in the following fields:

259

Companies in California licensed
technologies developed at UCLA

Third Mission & Impact

A university's "third mission" is its larger social responsibility that extends beyond conventional teaching and research. It emphasizes how the university interacts with the local community and the global community.

#4

UCLA is the fourth largest employer in LA County

\$4 Billion

Total economic impact in the city of Los Angeles

\$11 Billion

Total economic impact in the state of California

Over 72,700

Full-time jobs supported by the spending activity of UCLA

24

Startups launched using UCLA-developed technology

251

First-Generation Undergraduates

\$33 Billion

Total startup valuations built on UCLA's technology since 2000

Economical impact: according to a report by Beacon Economics (in 2016-2017 fiscal year), shows that UCLA is responsible for over **\$11 billion** of total economic impact on the state of California, including **\$4 billion** of economic impact in Los Angeles. Also, start-up valuations built on UCLA's technologies since 2000 reach a total of **\$33 billions**. Furthermore, it emerged from the studies that UCLA is the **fourth** largest employer in L.A., if we consider the impact of UCLA Health Sciences. The report also founded that **24 startups** using UCLA-developed technology were launched during the 2016-2017 fiscal year, and that 70 UCLA inventions were launched on the market for commercial use.

Third Mission & Impact

Improving the health and well-being of all Californians

The health care system at UCLA Health is **one of the most sophisticated and extensive in the world**. Modern patient care, research findings that lead to novel treatments and diagnoses, and the education of the next generation of health care workers are the goals.

**MORE THAN
260
CLINICS**

Primary and specialty care services are provided by these clinics throughout the Central Coast and Southern California.

Our Annual Impact

3.5 MILLION OUTPATIENT CLINIC VISITS

757,200 Unique Patient Visits

73,700 Emergency Department Visits

37,600 Inpatient Hospitalizations

UCLA HEALTH R&D

UCLA Health offers access to technology and treatments that may not be available elsewhere. Examples are here provided:

CANCER CARE TISSUE MATCHING GENE THERAPY TRANSPLANTS
UCLA(2023),UCLA Health

Financial aids to students

45% of students pay no tuition

UCLA Financial Aid and Scholarships is committed to supporting students in their academic endeavors by providing grants, scholarships, and other forms of financial assistance to help cover the cost of education. By giving students access to financial resources and counseling services, this office helps the university meet its enrollment and retention targets and increase the likelihood that students will succeed in pursuing their higher education objectives. There are **four type of financial aids**:

LET'S MAKE
**UCLA
HAPPEN**

WHO GETS UNDERGRADUATE AID AT UCLA?

63% receive UCLA financial aid

68% of students graduate with no loan debt

100% of families earning less than \$80k pay no tuition

UCLA (2023), Undergraduate Admission

Scholarships

Grants

Loans

Part- time student job

UCLA Environmental Responsibility

What is it Sustainability about?

Sustainability is the integration of environmental health, social equity and economic vitality to create thriving, healthy, diverse and resilient communities for this generation and generations to come.

- University of California, Los Angeles Sustainability Charter

An increasing number in LEED certifications

What is LEED?

LEED (Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design) is the world's most widely spread green building rating system. A whole sector of dedicated businesses and individuals are supporting LEED certification, which is a widely accepted indicator of sustainability accomplishment and is opening doors to new market opportunities.

17 Platinum, 33 Gold and 11 Silver

- Total number of LEED certifications

More can be found on their website by clicking on their logo here

Climate policy progress

UCLA was able to keep emissions below 1990 levels even with the return to campus. The renewable rate agreement with the Los Angeles Department of Water and Power was a significant factor in the **reduction of 7,674 metric tons of CO₂e in 2021**.

Maintaining energy efficiency initiatives through the **Smart Buildings and Labs Program**—of which three buildings have been completed and seven are under construction—was another factor. **Reduced emissions** were a result of hybrid and remote work. Therefore, the Los Angeles Department of Water and Power presented UCLA with an award in 2022 for **Leadership in Energy Efficiency**.

CLIMATE PROTECTION – EMISSIONS

ENERGY USE INTENSITY (EUI)

Sustainability plan

UCLA has created numerous plans and projects to assist these efforts, such as a Zero Waste Plan, Water Action Plan, Carbon Neutrality Plan, and Sustainable Transportation Plan, among others. In 2022 UCLA combined all of them for the first time into a thorough sustainability strategy for the campus that links operations, community involvement, and academics. In addition to highlighting the connections between human and environmental health, the plan starts the process of integrating justice, equity, diversity, and inclusion into our sustainability policies and initiatives.

1,000+

BRUINS ENGAGED IN DEVELOPING UCLA'S SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

At UCLA, sustainability fosters programs that improve the community, the environment, and financial responsibility. In addition to launching a more integrated strategy for the future, this sustainability plan acknowledges the fruitful legacy of that work. The University of California, the City and County of Los Angeles, higher education, and the global community are all places where UCLA is dedicated to promoting sustainability.

By clicking on this symbol further information will be provided about the sustainability plan and the scope UCLA referred here above

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This work was completed as part of the Public Management course at the School of Advanced Studies (SAA), University of Turin, under the supervision of Prof. Valerio Brescia. The elements presented in this assignment have been developed in accordance with the guidelines defined by Professors Paolo Biancone, Silvana Secinaro, Valerio Brescia, and Davide Calandra.